

Consumer Perception on Drinking Water in Sustainable Tetra Pak Packaging: A Case Study on Product Development of Indonesian Beverage Company

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ABSTRACT: The demand for Packaged Drinking Water (PDW) in Indonesia continues to grow due a substantial increase in the population and the challenge of accessing safe drinking water. This creates a larger opportunity to the water market industry, but also to an increase in the plastic pollution crisis. As a response to this, the Indonesian Government has issued updated regulations on waste management to address the emergency on plastic pollution. In line with the situations, an Indonesian beverage company is planning to launch their innovation on water products in sustainable Tetra Pak packaging. However, as this is going to be the first product to be launched in Indonesia, consumers' perception and expectation towards the product needs to be explored to be able to decide on the appropriate marketing strategy. This research aimed to decide the appropriate marketing strategy for the sustainable drinking water product by identifying the consumer perception of a product and how several factors within the perception could impact their intention to buy and their decision to purchase. For this purpose, a preliminary qualitative method (semi-structured interview) and quantitative method (questionnaire) were conducted and analyzed through PLS - SEM. The results showed that environmental awareness and packaging are the two attributes within consumer perception that significantly influence purchase intention. Based on the findings, a Green Marketing Mix Strategy should be applied. Using the 4P (Product, Promotion, Price and Place) approach, the solution would involve (1) Green Campaign, (2) Brand Ambassador, Influencer and KOL Marketing, (3) Event Marketing, (4) Packaging Design Collaboration (5) Value-Based Pricing, and (6) Setting Up Sales Channel.

KEYWORDS: Consumer Perception, Green Beverage Product, PLS – SEM, Purchase Intention, Purchase Decision.

INTRODUCTION

Packaged drinking water (PDW) industry, also known as Air Mineral Dalam Kemasan (AMDK), has a fairly large market share within the Indonesian beverage industry group with a market share of 85% [1]. The demand for PDW in Indonesia is continuously growing, in which a substantial proportion of the demand due to the increase in population and the challenge of accessing safe water [2]. In conjunction with the growth of bottled water production, the amount of plastic waste has also escalated significantly. As a result, the Indonesian Government issued updated regulations on waste management to minimize plastic pollution. In response to these situations, a green initiative is being developed by a beverage company, as they are developing the first PDW product with Tetra Pak sustainable carton packaging to be launched in Indonesia. In pursuance of the product to be accepted in the market, the marketing strategy implemented by the company should be adjusted to meet the consumers expectations. To delve deeper into the potential market, the consumers' perception towards the product was being analyzed by PLS-SEM. Several attributes within consumer perception that contribute to purchase intention and purchase decision were being examined. These attributes include packaging, price, eco-awareness, availability, and brand trust. Then, a Green Marketing Mix and Strategy method is being suggested, as it is the most suitable approach to optimize its sales within the market industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW

It is vital for the company to understand the consumers' perception toward the product, as it would determine the consumers' purchase intention, which is also related to whether the product could successfully penetrate the market in Indonesia. Consumer perceptual variables that have been identified include price-quality perception, value, perceived price fairness, self-perception, product familiarity, brand loyalty, perceived risk associated with product purchase, and general deal proneness [3]. Therefore, several factors

of consumer perception would be examined as it would influence purchase intention as well as decisions. These include packaging, price, environmental awareness, availability, and brand trust.

A. Packaging

Packaging is a critical aspect of a product which acts as a vehicle in communicating to customers [4]. Kotler and Keller [5] emphasized the importance of product packaging and its attributes such as design, colour, form, and information, to the extent that they defined packaging as the fifth “P” in marketing mix. According to Rokka and Uusitalo [6], as customers understand more on the various purposes of packaging, opinions on packaging solutions are more appreciated.

There are different aspects in packaging that contribute to the awareness of consumers. Findings show that there are 3 significant aspects that are found to be attractive. This includes ‘easy to re-seal’ (27%), ‘easy to open’ (26%) and ‘packaging size’ (24%). Meanwhile, the ones taken for granted such as product protection (8%) and information (3%) were probably overlooked as only a few mentioned [7]. On the contrary, a recent study found that the aspects that have a direct influence on consumers’ buying decisions are printed information, followed by the materials used in the packaging, environmental labelling, innovation design, background image, and uniqueness shape respectively [8]. Early studies showed that transparent packaging is seen as more attractive [9] and trustworthy [10]. Nonetheless, another study found that transparent packaging was identified as leading to negative product evaluations [11].

The most basic types of packaging, such as the plastic bag and traditional Tetra Brik are known to receive high valuations at the moment of purchases [12]. Furthermore, it is also stated that consumers rely on packaging as they make decisions to purchase products such as perfumes, soft drinks, and other food products. One example is Evian, which has reached an agreement with the designer Courrèges to launch a special edition of the bottle that will allow it to be sold in exclusive establishments at a higher price. This example shows that packaging promotes differentiation among competitors. Results show that the use of packaging that facilitates product use, such as the Tetra Brik with a cap, produces product satisfaction and loyalty and exercises the greatest influence at the moment of purchase and after usage. Similarly with the prior case, the PDW that the beverage company plans to launch is made of renewable resources. The sustainability of their packaging solutions would have an impact on the pricing, as the material is different to their current PET bottle.

B. Price

Price is the value of money that is being imposed on a product or service charged to the consumers [13]. The high to low price range of a product may have a massive impact on a customer's decision to purchase a product or service, depending on how individuals perceive that price [14]. As a result, there are several pricing strategies that could be applied in setting up pricing. This includes premium pricing, penetration pricing, economy pricing and skimming strategy [15]. Premium pricing occurs when there is an application of setting a high price in a segment or industry that has a strong competitive advantage, whereas penetration pricing is where the price is set low to rapidly gain market share. Meanwhile, economy pricing is a strategy to target the mass market by setting a low price due to a low-cost production. Lastly, skimming strategies occur when a product is charged high initially then decreases over time.

C. Eco-Awareness

Environmental awareness is a behavior that is shown and incorporated by individuals to their surroundings on a daily basis as a response to environmental information [16]. Xu, Prybutok, and Blankson [17] found that environmental awareness has a positive impact on the purchase intention of customers towards a green product. Furthermore, their results showed that the consumers’ intention to purchase a green product is related to the perceived quality of the product and the self-image of the consumer. Therefore, green marketing may create a significant impact in consumers’ buying intention of PDW in Indonesia to some degree, in which, sustainability increases consumer preference depending on the type of benefit that consumers value most in the product category Luchs et al. (2010).

D. Availability

Utama (2012) defined availability as the ability of a company to provide product accessibility in order to accommodate consumer demand [18]. On the customer point of view, perceived availability refers to the degree in which a consumer feels that a certain product can easily be obtained or consumed [19]. Ton and Raman [20] argued that if the availability status of a product is high, it

would increase the probability of consumers finding and purchasing that desired product. Koschat [21] described this positive relationship between product availability and sales as the availability effect. On the other hand, Steinhart, Mazurky, and Kamins [22] propose that lack of product availability affects consumers' intention to purchase a product based on how that absence is seen, either it is related to the value of the product or the ease of purchasing it.

E. Brand Trust

Chauduri and Holbrook [23] define brand trust as consumers' willingness to rely on the brands ability in carrying out its claimed functions. Prior research findings show that there was a strong relationship between brand trust and purchase intention, as the trust towards a brand has developed, the rate of purchase intention would also increase [24]. Moreover, he stated that the strategies that are going to be implemented have to focus on improving the consumer's perception of brand trust, preference and perceived value to have a positive impact on purchase intention.

F. Purchase Intention

According to Morinez et al. (2006), purchase intention is a situation where a consumer desires to buy a particular product in a particular condition [25]. In relation to purchase intention on green products, previous study by D'souza et al. [26] stated that consumers' past experiences in purchasing green products may be "crucial " in forming a product-specific perception that would determine their future purchase intention. Therefore, previous interactions with green products experienced by consumers influence their purchases or use of green products. This study is also supported by Kim & Chung [27] as their study revealed that a consumer's past experiences with organic products strongly impact their intention to purchase organic personal care products. Furthermore, they stated that this finding provides evidence that a lifestyle is reflected in the consumers' consumption of patterns.

G. Purchase Intention & Purchase Decision

Numerous studies have found that customer desire to participate in transactions online will be a strong indicator of the consumer's real participation in an online transaction. [28]. In line with the study, Kim, Ferrin, and Rao (2007) revealed that purchase intention influences purchase decision significantly [29]. Previous research conducted by Komalasari, Christiano, and Ganiarto [30] investigated different factors that contributed to consumers' purchase intention in e-commerce platforms which affects purchase decision. Based on the findings, the researcher stated that as purchase intentions of a consumer increase, so is the purchase decision. Hence, it is important to focus on raising the customers' intention to purchase by ensuring their trust and building a better brand image.

Based on these findings, a conceptual framework and the hypotheses below is constructed.

Figure I. Conceptual Framework

This research aims to examine the hypotheses based on structural model diagrams. Due to the mediation variable, the indirect effect is also being included in the hypothesis.

A. Direct Effect Hypothesis

H1: Packaging (X1) influences Purchase Intention (M)

H2: Price (X2) influences Purchase Intention (M)

H3: Eco-Awareness (X3) influences Purchase Intention (M)

H4: Availability (X4) influences Purchase Intention (M)

H5: Brand Trust (X5) influences Purchase Intention (M)

B. Indirect Effect Hypothesis

H6: Purchase Intention (M) influences Purchase Decision (Y)

H7: The relationship between Packaging (X1) and Purchase Decision (Y) can be mediated by Purchase Intention (M)

H8: The relationship between Price (X2) and Purchase Decision (Y) can be mediated by Purchase Intention (M)

H9: The relationship between Eco-Awareness (X3) and Purchase Decision (Y) can be mediated by Purchase Intention (M)

H10: The relationship between Availability (X4) and Purchase Decision (Y) can be mediated by Purchase Intention (M)

H11: The relationship between Brand Trust (X5) and Purchase Decision (Y) can be mediated by Purchase Intention (M)

RESEARCH METHODS

The quantitative data will be analyzed with Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

SEM is divided into two types, CB-SEM and PLS-SEM. According to Dash and Paul [31], CB-SEM is used for theoretical testing, confirmation and rejection. In contrast, PLS-SEM is the appropriate approach for predictive analysis and theory development. Conceptually, PLS-SEM analysis similar to multiple regression analysis, as it is utilized to maximize explained variance in the dependent constructs but also to assess the data based on the constructed and characteristics of the measurement model).

Table I. Questionnaire Content

<i>Classification of Investigation</i>	<i>Contents of Investigation</i>
Demographic Data	Gender, Age, Expenses, Location, Mobility
Eco-Awareness	Perceived value on green products and lifestyle
Availability	Perceived importance of product availability
Packaging	Perceived quality and attractiveness of packaging
Price	Perceived price for sustainable drinking water
Brand Trust	Users Past Experience, Loyalty, & Satisfaction
Purchase Intention	Degree of Interest & Willingness to Buy
Purchase Decision	Decision to Buy

ANALYSIS

This chapter will mainly discuss the results that were analyzed with SEM. The analysis will cover the characteristics of the participants, the evaluation of the outer measurement model, and the evaluation of the inner measurement model.

PARTICIPANT CHARACTERISTICS

The criteria of sample in this research are as follows: Men or Women aged between 18-65 and are active Indonesian citizen. Through surveys conducted according to the sample criteria, this research has gathered the response of 199 participants. The majority of respondents are aged between 23 – 28 years old (n=119, 59.8%). The majority of respondents are located in Bandung, East Java (n=50, 25,%). Most of the participants' occupations are university students (n=73, 35.7%) and private sector employee (n=73, 35.7%). Most respondents travel two to three times a week (n=53, 26,6%). The average monthly purchase of PDW for the majority of respondents are higher than 10 bottles per month (n=59, 29,6%). The majority of respondents stated that a sustainable PDW should be priced between Rp. 5.000 – Rp. 7.000 (n=82, 41.2%).

THE EVALUATION OF MEASUREMENT MODEL (OUTER MODEL)

Outer model evaluation is carried out to see the relationship between latent variables and their indicators. Convergent validity with reflective indicators can be seen from the correlation between the indicator score and the total construct score. An indicator is said to be valid if it has a loading value (λ) above 0.7.

A. Convergent and Validity Analysis

Table II. Loading Factor Analysis

	Loading Factor							SE	P-Value
	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	M	Y		
X1.1	(0.844)							0.060	<0.001
X1.2	(0.844)							0.060	<0.001
X2.1		(0.749)						0.061	<0.001
X2.2		(0.749)						0.061	<0.001
X3.1			(0.783)					0.061	<0.001
X3.2			(0.820)					0.061	<0.001
X3.3			(0.759)					0.061	<0.001
X3.4			(0.826)					0.060	<0.001
X3.5			(0.776)					0.061	<0.001
X3.6			(0.801)					0.061	<0.001
X3.7			(0.602)					0.063	<0.001
X3.9			(0.678)					0.062	<0.001
X4.1				(0.719)				0.062	<0.001
X4.2				(0.719)				0.062	<0.001
X5.1					(0.923)			0.059	<0.001
X5.2					(0.941)			0.059	<0.001
X5.3					(0.897)			0.060	<0.001
X5.4					(0.915)			0.059	<0.001
M1						(0.783)		0.061	<0.001
M2						(0.783)		0.061	<0.001
Y1							(0.771)	0.061	<0.001
Y2							(0.750)	0.061	<0.001
Y3							(0.774)	0.061	<0.001
Y4							(0.659)	0.062	<0.001

Based on Table II above, it can be concluded that the loading factor value of the relationship between the indicator variable and each of the construct has a loading factor value (λ) ≥ 0.5 and has a significant p-value, which is smaller than the error level (α) of the study, namely 0, 05. Thus, these indicators can be said to be valid for measuring the constructs.

Divergent validity is then analysed by evaluating the cross-loading value to assess whether the construct has high discriminant validity. High discriminant validity is obtained by comparing the cross loading on each indicator. If the cross-loading value of an indicator with the latent variable is greater than the cross-loading value on the latent variable itself, the indicator cannot measure the latent variable properly. The results of cross loading can be shown in Table III.

Table III. Cross-Loading Factor Analysis

	Loading Factor						
	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	M	Y
X1.1	(0.844)	0.037	-0.228	0.273	-0.011	-0.403	0.072
X1.2	(0.844)	-0.037	0.228	-0.273	0.011	0.403	-0.072
X2.1	-0.342	(0.749)	-0.051	-0.221	-0.091	-0.285	0.760
X2.2	0.342	(0.749)	0.051	0.221	0.091	0.285	-0.760
X3.1	-0.233	0.078	(0.781)	-0.154	-0.038	0.030	0.283
X3.2	-0.065	0.032	(0.820)	-0.057	-0.043	0.044	-0.046
X3.3	-0.255	0.043	(0.759)	-0.077	-0.030	-0.152	0.502
X3.4	0.297	0.018	(0.826)	-0.148	-0.052	-0.160	-0.181
X3.5	-0.191	0.069	(0.776)	-0.012	-0.002	0.136	0.166
X3.6	-0.139	-0.218	(0.801)	0.072	0.040	-0.011	0.195
X3.7	0.479	-0.050	(0.602)	0.144	-0.052	0.088	-0.577
X3.9	0.250	0.024	(0.678)	0.315	0.194	0.055	-0.519
X4.1	-0.114	0.148	-0.114	(0.719)	0.007	-0.016	-0.045
X4.2	0.114	-0.148	0.114	(0.719)	-0.007	0.016	0.045
X5.1	-0.169	0.020	-0.034	0.017	(0.923)	0.022	0.107
X5.2	0.121	0.040	0.033	-0.025	(0.941)	-0.015	-0.109
X5.3	0.185	-0.018	0.156	-0.029	(0.897)	-0.023	-0.137
X5.4	-0.135	-0.044	-0.134	0.037	(0.915)	0.016	0.138
M1	-0.584	0.037	-0.228	0.273	-0.011	(0.783)	0.072
M2	0.584	-0.037	0.228	-0.273	0.011	(0.783)	-0.072
Y1	-0.683	-0.180	0.168	0.114	-0.004	0.082	(0.771)
Y2	1.104	0.037	-0.228	0.273	-0.011	-0.403	(0.750)
Y3	0.584	-0.037	0.228	-0.273	0.011	0.403	(0.774)
Y4	-1.143	0.212	-0.205	-0.124	0.004	-0.110	(0.659)

The bold values in Table III show the square-root of AVE, which is higher than the estimated correlation values, thus demonstrating the discriminant validity of constructs involved in the proposed measurement. Overall, these results satisfy all requirements for establishing the validity and reliability of reflective measurement models.

THE EVALUATION OF MEASUREMENT MODEL (INNER MODEL)

Evaluation of the inner model is carried out after the evaluation of the measurement model has been completed and meets the requirements. Based on the analysis that has been done, it can be seen the results of the structural equation path diagram in this study. Figure II shows the structural equation path diagram of Packaging (X1), Price (X2), Eco-Awareness (X3), Availability (X4), Brand Trust (X5) with the causal relation to Purchase Decision (Y) and Purchase Intention (M) as the mediator variable.

Figure II. PLS Structural Equation Path Diagram with WarpPLS Software

Table V. Hypotheses Assessment of Structural Model

Direct Effect					
H	Path	Coefficient	P-value	Result	Status
H ₁	X1 -> M	0,69	<0,001	Significant	Supported
H ₂	X2 -> M	0,10	0,075	Insignificant	Unsupported
H ₃	X3 -> M	0,13	0,027	Significant	Supported
H ₄	X4 -> M	0,00	0,498	Insignificant	Unsupported
H ₅	X5 -> M	0,00	0,482	Insignificant	Unsupported
H ₆	M -> Y	0,73	<0,001	Significant	Supported
Indirect Effect					
H	Path	Coefficient	P-value	Result	Status
H ₇	X1 -> M -> Y	0,51	<0,001	Significant	Supported
H ₈	X2 -> M -> Y	0,07	0,070	Insignificant	Unsupported
H ₉	X3 -> M -> Y	0,10	0,024	Significant	Supported
H ₁₀	X4 -> M -> Y	0,00	0,498	Insignificant	Unsupported
H ₁₁	X5 -> M -> Y	0,00	0,481	Insignificant	Unsupported

Table V shows p-value for each variable relationship is shown. This value is compared with the value of the error rate (λ) research, namely = 0.05. If the p-value is less than 0.05 then the relationship is significant which means the hypothesis is accepted and vice versa when the p-value is greater than 0.05 then the relationship is not significant and the hypothesis is rejected.

The next evaluation is to look at the reliability of a variable to show internal consistency to measure the instrument used. According to Maholtra [32], reliability refers to the extent to which a scale produces consistent results if repeated measurements are made. Reliability is assessed by determining the proportion of systematic variation in a scale. This is done by determining the association

between scores obtained from different administrations of the scale. If the association is high, the scale yields consistent results and is therefore reliable. In this study, a variable is said to be quite reliable if the variable has a composite reliability value > 0.7 and also an AVE > 0.5 . Following are the results of reliability testing on each latent variable with the help of WarpPLS software.

Table VI. R-Square Value

Variable	R-Square (R^2) value
Purchase Intention (M)	0.62
Purchase Decision (Y)	0.53

According to the results, the R^2 value was obtained for the Purchase Intention (M) and Purchase Decision (Y) variables. The R^2 value indicates the amount of effective contribution given, the explanation for the R^2 value for each variable is as follows:

1. The R^2 value for the Purchase Intention (M) variable is 0.62, which indicates that the effective contribution of the Packaging (X1), Price (X2), Eco Awareness (X3), Availability (X4) and Brand Trust (X5) variables to the Purchase Intention (M) variable is 62%
2. The R^2 value for the Purchase Decision (Y) variable is 0.53, which indicates that the effective contribution of the Packaging (X1), Price (X2), Eco Awareness (X3), Availability (X4), Brand Trust (X5) and Purchase Intention (M) variables to the variable Purchase Decision (Y) is 53%.

FINDINGS

Based on the findings analyzed by PLS-SEM, evidence shows that Packaging (X1) is an important element for consumers in their purchase intention. This finding is consistent with previous research [33] who found that visual packaging affects consumer buying behavior towards a product. Most of the respondents think that the attractiveness of the packaging is a factor that brings them into considerations in buying the product, as it interests them. Furthermore, the result has also shown that Eco-Awareness (X3) is a strong predictor to consumers purchase intention. This corresponds to the findings by Rokka & Uusitalo [34], in which they revealed that consumers favored environmentally labeled packaging as the most crucial factor when making their decision. In response to this, Noor, Masuod and Said [35] confirmed that purchase decisions of eco-friendly products are significantly associated with consumer awareness towards the environment, such as supporting the less harmful products and recycling activities. In addition, this study also confirms that purchase intention is related to purchase decision. Hence, both Packaging (X1) Eco-Awareness (X3) factors influence purchase decision, and it can be mediated by purchase intention.

CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATION

The research has explored consumer perception on green product. Results shows that environmental awareness and packaging are the two predictors that influence purchase intention. In order for the product to be able to penetrate in Indonesian market, implementing a Green Marketing Strategy is recommended. This could be done by management by doing a green campaign on social media. Furthermore, event marketing should also be implemented, such as hosting a packaging competition to generate awareness and also as a way to increase consumers' attractiveness to the

However, there are several issues that occur in this research. First, the survey participants were mostly students aged between 21-28. Hence, it did not portray the real representation of the population. Therefore, the results may not be applied across entire population. Second, the survey result shows that the contribution of the factors or variables discussed in this study to Purchase Decision is still quite low, namely only 53%. This indicates that the remaining 47% may be influenced by many other factors not discussed in the study. Future research might identify the specific potential market for this particular product through STP, and narrow down the market along with its certain level of green awareness. Furthermore, future research may explore other factors that might influence Purchase Decision.

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